

«Методы производства биочара: сравнение существующих современных технологий»

Bio-char production methods: a comparison between the existing modern techniques

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Аннотация

Биочар - это древесный уголь, образующийся в результате сжигания биомассы в условиях, когда кислорода мало или нет. Сельскохозяйственные и лесные отходы являются идеальным сырьем, поскольку они производят биоуголь, пригодный в качестве добавки к почве (Verheijen et al., 2010). В результате пиролиза образуются различные побочные продукты: биоуголь, жидкое топливо и газ (Demirbas et al., 2002). Среди побочных продуктов биочар является наиболее привлекательным из-за его экономических и экологических преимуществ: с одной стороны, при внесении в почву биочар улучшает свои физические и химические характеристики, а с другой стороны действует как поглотитель углерода, который помогает смягчить изменение климата (Чан и др., 2008). В отличие от ранее использовавшихся методов, пиролизом можно управлять для увеличения количества производимого биочара, снижения негативных воздействий и минимизации использования внешних источников энергии (Qian et al., 2015). Три наиболее эффективные технологии, используемые для пиролиза биомассы: пиролиз в печи, пиролиз с использованием микроволнового излучения и гидротермальная карбонизация (Meuer et al., 2011). Эти три метода сравниваются с точки зрения выхода их побочных продуктов; количество внешней энергии, которое им

требуется; их возможные негативные последствия; и стоимость машин, используемых в их производстве.

Ключевые слова: биочар, пиролиз, микроволновая печь, гидротерм, печи, методы производства

Abstract

Biochar is a charcoal resulting from the combustion of biomass under conditions of little or no oxygen. Agricultural and forestry waste are the ideal feedstock as they produce biochar suitable for soil amendment (Verheijen et al., 2010). As a result of the pyrolysis different byproducts are created: biochar, liquid fuel, and gas (Demirbas et al., 2002). Among the byproducts biochar is the most attractive due to its economic and environmental benefits, on one hand when applied to the soil, the biochar improves its physical and chemical characteristics and on the other hand acts as a carbon sink which helps mitigating climate change (Chan et al., 2008). In contrast to formerly used methods pyrolysis can be controlled to increase the amount of biochar produced, reducing negative impacts and minimizing the use of external sources of energy (Qian et al., 2015). The three most efficient technologies used to pyrolyze biomass are: kiln pyrolysis, microwave assisted pyrolysis, and hydrothermal carbonization (Meyer et al., 2011). These three methods are compared in terms of their byproducts yield; the amount of external energy they require; their possible negative effects; and the costs of the machines employed in their production.

Keywords: biochar, pyrolysis, microwave, hydrothermal, kilns, production methods

Theoretical framework of the study

There is a large body of peer-reviewed literature quantifying and describing the crop yield benefits of biochar-amended soil (Sohi et al., 2010). Field trials using biochar have been conducted in the tropics over the past several years (Bass et al., 2016). Most studies show positive in terms of soil improvement, increased crop yields and carbon

sequestration. There evidence of the effectiveness of this technology dates back to thousands of years ago when it was traditional to use charcoal in soils. The most well-known example is the fertile Terra Preta soils in Brazil (Joseph et al., 2015), but Japan also has a long tradition of using charcoal in soil, a tradition that is being revived and has been exported over the past 20 years to countries such as Costa Rica (Ogawa et al., 2010). The Brazilian and Japanese traditions together provide long-term evidence of positive biochar impact on soils.

Regarding the carbon sequestration potential of biochar it has been calculated that sustainable biochar implementation could offset a maximum of 12% of anthropogenic GHG emissions on an annual basis. Over the course of 100 years, this amounts to roughly 130 petagrams of CO₂-equivalents. The study assessed the maximum sustainable technical potential utilizing globally available biomass from agriculture and forest (Woolf et al., 2010).

When talking about biochar production methods several technologies are being used and experimented to reduce costs and environmental impacts while increasing efficiency. The process of turning biomass into biochar is called pyrolysis and modernly it can be done in three ways: kilns, Microwave assisted pyrolysis, and HTC (hydrothermal carbonization). The main differences among them are the proportion of byproducts resulting from the process (gas, liquid fuel) and the time employed (Meyer et al., 2011). It is expected that further understanding of the feedstock-biochar relation, as well as the wider biochar-soil-climate relation would bring along technological and managerial developments allowing for significant reductions in biochar production costs and its wider use both as soil amendment and carbon sequestration tool (Sohi et al., 2009).

Investigation methodology

This qualitative study explores the different methods of biochar production. In the first stage it involved the review of scientific and technical literature, the method selected as the object of the study complied with two fundamental conditions: the process is anaerobic and uses agricultural or forestry waste as their source of feedstock. The second part of the research involved direct contact with biochar producers who provided information about the methods they employ, the feedstock they use, the type of equipment they use and the costs of running the production. The third stage of the research dealt with the identification of the stages of production and the relevant factors to be included for the costs analysis. In the fourth stage, the production costs of each method

were calculated. Finally, the data was analyzed and different biochar production methods were compared regarding their characteristics, feasibility according to the resources they require, and their biochar and sub-products' yield.

Results and Discussion

Transforming biomass (plants or manure) into char through combustion is an antique technology that has been used by farmers in different places and times. Char has since the beginning being a multipurpose technology which allows people to create a material that can be easily store and provides can be used both as fuel, soil amended and practical way to manage agricultural or forestry waste (Antal et al., 2003). However, the former methods of bio-char production are far from optimal as their yield is small compare to the feedstock inputted and release a large fraction of pollutant elements into the atmosphere. The root cause of such inefficiency and polluting effect is that the process is conducted aerobically. Most traditional methods are carried out in open or semi-open systems, which allows for too much oxygen to enter the combustion causing a large portion of the potentially preservable carbon to burn out before taking the form of char as well as allowing both liquid and solid components to turn into volatile particles that fly out to end up in the atmosphere or fall down on soil or water bodies (causing diverse problems such as increasing the greenhouse effect, or reacting with other elements).

Thus, I order to improve the technology it was necessary to contain the process to avoid both the excess of oxygen in the combustion and the release of emissions. Such anaerobic combustion is called pyrolysis and three main technologies have been tuned to obtain higher yields while reducing polluting emissions. Pyrolysis corresponds to the decomposition of biomass under the action of heat and in total or partial absence of oxygen to produce: biochar, bio-oils, and gases. The proportion of those different products depends strongly on the specific production method use as well as the way the process is manipulated to obtain a higher yield of one of the sub-products (Lehmann et al., 2015).

Kilns pyrolysis method: In the pyrolysis (thermal decomposition) of wood we can get charcoal, liquid and gas. Liquid products appear partly in the drop phase, partly in pairs forming the vapor-gas mixture together with non-condensable gases (Brown et al.,2012)

The pyrolysis usually involves four steps.

- **Drying of wood:** temperature not higher than 150°C; endothermic process; the composition of the wood is almost unchanged.

- The initial stage of the decomposition of wood: temperature from 150 to 270-275°C; endothermic process; the decomposition of hemicelluloses and individual fragments of lignin begins; low-molecular products (water, carbon oxides, methanol, acetic acid, etc.) are formed.

- The pyrolysis stage: temperature from 270-275°C to 450°C; the process is exothermic; there is an intensive decomposition of cellulose and lignin with the formation of the coal residue.

- Calcination of coal: the temperature depends on the type of the equipment and lies between 450-600°C; the cleavage of residual functional groups from the carbon physical structure; endothermic and exothermic reactions proceed at the same time, the total balance of the stage is endothermic.

The composition and properties of thermolysis products depends on the quality of wood, the size of the particles and the initial moisture content, the heating rate, the time while feedstock is processing under temperature in each stage, the final heating temperature, the circulation rate of the gas flow through the wood layer, and other factors (Tab.1).

Table 1: Products of pyrolysis from different kind of wood feedstock.

Feedstock		Products of pyrolysis, %				
		Coal	Resins	Volatile components	Gases	Liquid
Spruce	Wood	37,9	15,3	6,3	18,2	22,3
	Tar	42,5	18,4	1,9	19,8	17,4
Pine	Wood	38	16,7	6,2	17,7	21,4
	Tar	40,5	18,2	5,7	19,7	15,9
Birch	wood	33,6	14,3	12,3	17	22,8
	Tar	37,9	24	4,7	18,6	14,8
Aspen	wood	33	16	7,3	20,4	23,3

* This data should be regarded as indicative because the yield of products also depends on the growth conditions, the age of the trees and even on the part of the trunk.

The process significantly depends on the initial moisture content of wood. This value varies from 75% for freshly delivered feedstock to 15% for air-dry wood. The feedstock of pyrolysis should be dried. The increased humidity of wood decreases the quality of charcoal (occurrence of fracturing).

The composition and yield of the final products largely depends on the residence time of the vapor-gas mixture in the hot zone. It can be argued that a relatively low temperature (200-400 ° C) and a long process duration contribute to the formation of coal, whereas gases are formed at

temperatures above 600 ° C. Resins will prevail at a more moderate temperature (400-600 ° C), high heating rate and short residence time.

The maximum carbon content in coal is about 95%.

Since wood has a low thermal conductivity. The heat spreads slowly in it and until the exothermic stage is reached we need a constant heat source to maintain the process.

However, coal whose calcination is completed at 450-550 ° C is quite suitable for most areas of consumption (Tab.2).

Table 2: Char yield in Kgs from kiln pyrolysis at different temperatures.

T, °C	Carbon	Ash
350	73,3	2,0
400	77,3	2,1
450	81,6	2,4
500	85,9	2,7
550	88,1	2,9
600	90,3	3
650	91,4	3,1
700	92,3	3,1
750	92,7	3,2
800	93,4	3,3
850	95,4	3,3
900	15,5	3,4

In industrial production the output of coal is often noticeably less than quoted above. The most common causes are the ingress of air oxygen into the machines, as a result part of the coal burns out, also features of the regime and losses during overloads, excluding from the balance the coal dust.

When comparing three different kilns for biochar production using heat pyrolysis method which come in 3 models, 100-MK1, 100-MK2, and 500-MK1 and produce from about 100 kgs to 750 kgs per batch if wood is used as the feedstock. In the first case, the 100-MK1 can process only split wood, whereas the other models can process a much wider variety of feedstock. Prices for these batch kilns range from about 492 463 to 4 924 632 rubles, excluding shipping (according to the data provided by the producer in the first semester of 2018).

Table 3. Comparison between various capacity kilns: costs and characteristics

	<i>Batch Kiln 100-MK 1</i>	Batch Kiln 100-MK 2	Batch Kiln 500-MK 1
Batch time	8 hours	from 3 to 10 hours	variable, up to 8 hours
Moisture content	up to 40%	up to 60%	up to 60%
Feedstock size	logs, up to 30cm in length and 10cm in diameter	wood shavings or rice husk, up to 30cm length logs	from rice husk, wood shavings and wood chip up to 30cm length logs
Feedstock type	wood	most biomass	most types of biomass
Feedstock volume	1,5m ³	1,5m ³	two kiln bodies or retorts of 6 cubic meters each
Fuel source	logs, up to 15cm in length and 5cm in diameter	logs, up to 15cm in length and 8cm in diameter	woodchip
Char yield	up to 100kg per burn	up to 100kg per burn	up to 750 kg per cycle (per 6 m ³ retort)
Infrastructure used	handheld leaf blower (provided with the kiln)	3 electric fans and a generator (provided with the kiln)	4 electric fans and a generator (provided with the kiln)
Price	492 463 rubles	1 641 544 rubles	4 924 632

Microwave assisted pyrolysis method: Microwave – assisted pyrolysis (MAP) is a new thermochemical process that converts biomass to bio-oil. Compared with the conventional electrical heating pyrolysis, MAP is more rapid, efficient, selective, controllable, and flexible (Motasemi et al., 2013).

Recently, a new pyrolysis technique, microwave assisted pyrolysis (MAP), was developed and it has drawn serious attention because of its advantages over the traditional electrical heating methods. For conventional electrical heating methods, heat is transferred from high temperature gas to the fuel particle surface through convection mechanism and it is then further transferred from the outside surface to the in-side core through conduction mechanism. A temperature gradient from outside to in-side of the feedstock particle is formed because of the poor thermal conductivity of the feedstock material, and the released volatile diffuses from the inside core to the outside surface through a higher temperature region (Figure 3). For the microwave heating method, microwave penetrates the feedstock particle and microwave energy is transformed into heat inside the particle. Because of the heat loss effect of particle surface, heat constantly accumulates inside the feedstock and is transferred out-wards. A temperature gradient from inside to outside of feedstock particle is formed also because of the poor thermal conductivity of the feedstock material, and the re-leased volatile diffuses from the inside core to the outside surface through a lower temperature region (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of temperature distribution, heat transfer, and mass transfer in the conventional heating and microwave heating.

With the advantages it offers and the further research and development recommended, microwave – assisted pyrolysis has a bright future in production of bio-oils that can effectively narrow the energy gap and reduce negative environmental impacts of our energy production and application practice.

Beyond the technical and theoretical aspects of the production, when consulting producers about the Microwave assisted pyrolysis about production in practice significant differences were found in comparison to other methods. First, in contrast to heat pyrolysis processes it takes less

time and doesn't require additional fuel sources. In spite of a shorter production time, yields are lower than those obtained with the other more time consuming methods: biochar yield is merely 5% instead of the 13% in heat pyrolysis.

Table 4. Microwave assisted pyrolysis for Biochar production: costs and characteristics

Batch time	30 mins
Moisture content	Up to 85%
Feedstock size	Logs 11-15 cms
Feedstock type	most types of biomass
Feedstock volume	20 litres microwave system
Fuel source	Self-fueled
Char yield	From 5,94% to 7,48% of feedstock
Infrastructure used	1 m ³ , 6kw multimode-chamber
Price	633 898 rubbles

HTC for Biochar production: Hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) is similar to the natural process of fossil coal formation which lasted for millions of years in nature and can be accomplished within a matter of hours (Liu et al., 2013). At a temperature of 180-220 ° C, a pressure of 10-25 bar, without air access and with the addition of a catalyst, the biomass is dehydrated and carbonized for 6-12 hours to CO₂-neutral biochar.

The process begins with the preparation of biomass: mechanical impurities (sand, stones, etc.) are removed from it, then ground and wetted. The biomass is then sent to a HTC reactor (retort), in which a pressure of 10-25 bar and a temperature of 180-220 ° C is applied with steam.

With the competent regulation of the carbonization process, the released heat can be used to dry the coal or to generate electricity. Since the resulting coal can be mechanically dewatered, its final drying requires less thermal energy than the conventional drying process. The production process is characterized by almost 100% char yield: almost all carbon from organic biomass is transformed into biochar.

The advantages of HTC technology over other biomass processing technologies:

- high efficiency; does not need to pre-dry the biomass, which significantly reduces the cost of equipment;
- the ability to use a wide variety of biomass, including low-quality biomass, which is only suitable for disposal;
- ease of maintenance and low operating costs;

-high ecological compatibility of the technology, which excludes environmental pollution;

-the possibility of using a mixture consisting of different types of biomass.

In addition, the thermal energy produced during the exothermic process is used to dry the final product to the required humidity.

HTC technology allows processing not only plant biomass (wood, straw, etc.), but also organic waste from food production, as well as biomass with a very high moisture content (sewage and sewage sludge from both enterprises and settlements).

HTC is expedient for use in Russian conditions, primarily due to low requirements for raw materials (composition, moisture content), and also because of its high energy efficiency, simplicity and wide application possibilities in the domestic market.

According to the information obtained from producers that use the HTC it revealed that this production method has the highest yield and the lowest costs. However, it takes much more time than two other methods which can be crucial for producers in terms of running costs and longer times to put the product in the market specially if the competition uses a faster method.

Table 5. HTC (hidrotermical combustion) for biochar production: costs and characteristics

Batch time	From 6 to 12 hours
Moisture content	50 to 60%
Feedstock size	Logs 18-20 cms
Feedstock type	most types of biomass
Feedstock volume	1cm ³
Fuel source	Steam, flue gases and water
Char yield	60 to 90% of feedstock
Infrastructure used	Vacuum chamber for drying and impregnation
Price	65 661 rubbles

Comparing the three methods: Kilns, MAP, HTC

Three different types of biochar production methods were analyzed: Kilns pyrolysis method, MAP microwave assisted Pyrolysis, and HTC.

First, we compared the three methods in terms of their general characteristics such as feedstock, batch time, char yield, cost of production, which were found to be the most relevant.

Table 6. Comparison of general characteristics of Biochar production methods

	Heat pyrolysis	Microwave	HTC
Feedstock (wood), kg	1 000	1 000	1 000
Batch time, hours	3-8	0,5	6-12
Char yield, kg	130	60	800
Cost of production, USD	37 433,72	10 038,48	1 039,83
Cost of production, RUB	2 111 261,8	566 170,27	58 646,41

Considering the equipment required, feedstock, and running cost of each method, it can be observed that HTC is the cheapest.

Table 7. Cost comparison of Biochar production methods

RUB			
	Heat pyrolysis	Microwave	HTC
wood	7500	7500	7500
electricity per day	1000	1000	1000
work per day	4000	4000	4000
cost of land (1 hectar)	34900	34900	34900
equipment	2063861,8	518770,27	11246,41
USD			
wood	132,98	132,98	132,98
electricity per day	17,73	17,73	17,73
work per day	70,92	70,92	70,92
cost of land (1 hectar)	618,79	618,79	618,79
equipment	36593,29	9198,05	199,40

When the focus of the production is not the biochar itself but the subproducts the microwave assisted pyrolysis is the best alternative as fuel can be produced quickly and with high yields.

Table 8. Possible profit from additional byproducts

Parameters	Heat pyrolysis	Microwave	HTC
Oil	22,80%	75%	8%
Gas	17%	12,50%	12%
Market price of oil	240,8 per kg	240,8 per kg	240,8 per kg
Market price of gas	13,76 per kg	13,76 per kg	13,76 per kg
RUB			
Per 1 ton	54902,4 + 2339,2 =57241,6	180600+1720 =182320	19264+1651,2 =20915,2
USD			
Per 1 ton	1014,92	3232,62	370,84

Conclusion

Each process had its own advantages and disadvantages. Microwave pyrolysis is the fastest process but it has low char yield and high cost of production. It is a great alternative if the goal is to turn the biomass into fuel (gas, liquid). HTC and Kiln pyrolysis take much longer but produce the most biochar and are cheaper to implement. Among HTC and Kiln pyrolysis, HTC requires less additional processes (for the kiln feedstock must be pre-dried), less external sources of energy are used (most of the energy triggering and sustaining the combustion is internally generated while the kiln requires the use of electricity to run the machinery), the resulting biochar is chemically and structurally more homogeneous independently from the feedstock source (the type of biochar obtained with kilns may substantially vary depending on the feedstock). Yields obtained from HTC are as high as 90% which also implies a dramatic drop in possible emissions (making this process unsuitable for gas or liquid fuel production but ideal for the management of farm and forestry waste). Although technically more sophisticated the equipment required for HTC is less expensive than kilns, especially at large scale. However, HTC is a long process that can take up to 60% more time, and likely the

participation of workers with technical or scientific knowledge not because the technology is complex to operate but because it has been used mostly in experiments and not in much in agricultural practice.

It is expected that further understanding of the feedstock-biochar relation, as well as the wider biochar-soil-climate relation would bring along technological and managerial developments allowing for significant reductions in biochar production costs and its wider use both as soil amendment and carbon sequestration tool

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